

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF CONDUCTIVE ELECTROSPUN POLYPYRROLE NANOFIBERS CONTAINING MULTI-WALL CARBON NANOTUBES

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1 Introduction

Fiber-like structures with nano-size diameters, such as nanotubes, nanorods, and nanowires, have been the theme of great interest for a number of potential applications due to their high aspect ratios as well as unique properties such as high surface-to-volume ratios. Among them, nanofiber has been used in protective clothing, nanocomposites, optical sensors, biomedical applications including biomedicine, scaffolding for tissue growth, drug delivery systems, and for solar sails in space. As one of various applications, the fabrication of nanofiber using conductive polymer has recently been demonstrated in the design and construction of nanoelectronic devices. Electrospinning is a relatively simple and useful method for the formation of polymer nanofibers.

2 Experimentals

2.1 Materials.

The pristine Multi-wall carbon nanotube (MWNT) used in this work was supplied from Iljin Nanotech Co., Ltd (Seoul, Korea). The MWNT has the length of 10-50 mm and diameter of 10-20 nm. Aqueous polypyrrole (PPy) solution (5 wt.-% in water doped with proper dopants), poly(ethylene glycol) methyl ether (PEG; Mn = ca. 2,000) were purchased from Aldrich. Poly(ethylene oxide) (PEO), with an average molecular weight of ca. 900,000 g/mol, thionyl chloride were purchased from Acros Organics. All chemical reagents were used directly without further purification.

2.2 Preparation of oxidized MWNTs [(COOH)n-MWNT]

To remove the impurities such as metallic catalysts in the MWNT (95% purity), it was purified by acid treatment with the mixture of H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ (3:1; v/v). The mixture was stirred at 80 °C for 4 h. After cooling down to 25 °C, the mixture was poured to iced water and the mixture was vacuum-filtered through a 0.2 mm poly (tetrafluoroethylene) membrane. The treated MWNT was washed with mixture of H₂O and acetone several times.

2.3 Preparation of PEG tethered-MWNTs [(PEG)n-MWNT]

The acid treated MWNT [(COOH)n-MWNT] was prepared with excess SOCl₂ for 8 h under reflux, and then the residual SOCl₂ was removed by distillation under a reduced pressure to yield acyl chloride-functionalized MWNT [(COCl)n-MWNT] (2). 50 mg of PEG was added to the stirred suspension of [(ClOC)n-MWNT] (500 mg), anhydrous CH₂Cl₂ (20 mL), and several drops of dry Et₃N at 0 °C and then it was stirred at 25 °C for 48 h. The prepared MWNT was dispersed in excess CH₂Cl₂, filtered, and washed again to remove any adsorbed unreacted PEGs. The black solid was collected and dried in vacuo overnight at 40 °C to afford the PEG-tethered MWNT [(PEG)n-MWNT].

2.4 Preparation of Nanofibers

A typical electrospinning setup was used for this experiment. The apparatus for electrospinning consist of a syringe pump (KD Scientific Co.), a metal needle, a grounded target (drum type collector made by aluminum), and a high-voltage supply (Nano Technics Co., Korea). A voltage of 1-40 kV was applied to the polymer solution, and the distance between the needle tip and the target surface was adjusted between 10 and 25 cm. To remove the

impurities such as metallic catalysts in the MWNT (95% purity), it was purified by acid treatment with the mixture of H₂SO₄ and HNO₃ (3:1; v/v). The mixture was stirred at 80 °C for 4 h. After cooling down to 25 °C, the mixture was poured to iced water and the mixture was vacuum-filtered through a 0.2 mm poly (tetrafluoroethylene) membrane. The treated MWNT was washed with mixture of H₂O and acetone several times.

2.5 Characterization

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM; JEOL, JSH-6360A) was used to characterize the surface morphology and the diameters distribution of the electrospun nanofibers. Observations were carried out at 10–20 kV accelerating voltage and the samples had been coated with thin gold film. High resolution transmission electron microscope (HR-TEM; JEOL, JEM-3010) was performed at an accelerating voltage of 300 kV. The specimens for TEM analysis were prepared by direct deposition of the electrospun nanofibers onto a copper grid. The grid containing the fiber sample was allowed to dry at room temperature overnight. The electric conductivity of the compressed nanofiber mat was measured by using van der Pauw's four-probe method. The current through the sample was measured with a Keithley's 2400 Source Meter, which can measure currents as low as 10⁻¹¹. Each sample was measured ten times in different directions by applying the potential of 100 V and average value was calculated

3 Result and discussion

Figure 1 shows SEM images of the as-spun products from aqueous PPy/PEO (20:80; w/w) blend solution at various concentrations. At the concentrations lower than 1.0 wt.-% of PPy:PEO blend, electrospinning of such solutions resulted only in the formation of discrete beads. At such a low polymer concentration, the viscosity related to the degree of chain entanglement of polymer was not high enough to withstand the Coulombic stretching force acting on an infinitesimal segment of charged jet and it causes the jet stream to break up into smaller jets, which were rounded up to form bead shape as a result of the surface tension. Increasing the polymer

concentration over 1.0 wt. % up to 1.5 wt. % showed formation of beaded fibers due to the increased viscosity, hence the increased degree of chain entanglement, that was just enough to prevent the charged jet from totally breaking up.

To illustrate the effect of the blending ratio between PEO and PPy on the morphological appearance of the electrospun nanofibers, the various polymer blend ratios were selected as 80:20, 60:40, and 40:60.

Figure 1. SEM photographs of electrospun materials obtained from PPy:PEO (20:80; w/w) blends at concentrations of (a) 1, (b) 1.5, and (c) 2 wt.-%, from different blend ratios at 2 wt.-% concentration (d) 40:60, (e) 60:40.

Carbon nanotube(CNT) is considered as one-dimensional nanomaterials with a high aspect ratio, which is quite a bit longer than the diameter of electrospun nanofibers. For the nanofiber of carbon nanotube-polymer composite, it is important to have the oriented carbon nanotube along the axes of nanofibers. The electrospinning process is an effective method to generate this kind of composite nanofibers and Dror et al. established a model system to explain how the carbon nanotube-polymer composite nanofibers were formed by

electrospinning. When the carbon nanotubes and polymer are mixed in the solvent, the carbon nanotube is randomly oriented in the polymer solution. Due to elongation flow of the jet fluid during the electrospinning process, the nanotubes were oriented along the streamlines of the electrospun solution. TEM is an effective tool for observation of the carbon nanotube orientation in the electrospun nanofibers, since the carbon nanotube possesses a higher density compared with polymer matrix. Figure 2 shows TEM images of the MWNT embedded within the electrospun PPy:PEO (40:60 wt/wt) composite nanofibers containing 7 wt. % MWNT. As shown in Figure 2-a and 2-b, one can clearly see the MWNTs are well aligned along the axis of the electrospun nanofiber by the TEM bright-field image, in which MWNT formed a darker image rather than the PPy:PEO matrix due to different densities. Theoretically, carbon nanotube is considered to have the straight cylindrical structure with very high aspect ratio. However, the MWNTs formed by CVD catalytic pyrolysis of hydrocarbon compound are not straight shape. In most cases, the tubular structure of MWNT is bent or curved to some extent, and sometimes helical, since the carbon structure of carbon nanotubes are not completely composed of carbon hexagonal rings. Some pentagonal or heptagonal rings took the place of hexagonal rings to make the deformed tubular structure of carbon nanotube.[24] These deformed MWNTs has the morphology of the electrospun CNT-polymer composite nanofibers different from that of the neat polymer electrospun nanofibers as shown in Figure 2 (d-i). Especially, a highly winding or helical nanotube could not be embedded within the nanofiber by using electrospinning process as can be seen in Figure 2 (i). Therefore, in order to obtain the aligned morphology of carbon nanotube as well as smooth nanofiber surfaces in polymer composite nanofibers, the straight cylindrical shape of carbon nanotubes are preferred.

Figure 2. TEM photographs of of electrospun materials obtained from PPy:PEO (40:60; w/w) blends containing 7 wt.-% MWNT..

Conclusion

This work describes the electrospinning fabrication of nanofibers containing the multi-walled carbon nanotubes modified by poly(ethylene glycol). PPy/PEO (60:40 wt. %) nanofiber containing 7 wt. % of MWNT represents the nanostructure fabrication by utilizing carbon nanotubes as well as conducting polymer to achieve remarkably enhanced electric conductivity properties.

References CONCLUSION

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